

MXene and MoS_{3-x} Coated 3D-Printed Hybrid Electrode for Solid-State Asymmetric Supercapacitor

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Recently, 2D nanomaterials such as transition metal carbides or nitrides (MXenes) and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) have attracted ample attention in the field of energy storage devices specifically in supercapacitors (SCs) because of their high metallic conductivity, wide interlayer spacing, large surface area, and 2D layered structures. However, the low potential window ($\Delta V \approx 0.6$ V) of a MXene e.g., Ti₃C₂T_x limits the energy density of the SCs. Herein, asymmetric supercapacitors (ASCs) are fabricated by assembling the exfoliated Ti₃C₂T_x (Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x) as the negative electrode and transition metal chalcogenide (MoS_{3-x}) coated 3D-printed nanocarbon framework (MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF) as the positive electrode utilizing polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)/H₂SO₄ gel electrolyte, which provides a wide ΔV of 1.6 V. The Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x possesses wrinkled sheets which prevent restacking of Ti₃C₂T_x 2D layers. The MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF holds a porous structure and offers diffusion-controlled intercalated pseudocapacitance that enhances the overall capacitance. The 3D printing allows a facile fabrication of customized shaped MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF electrodes. Employing the advantages of the 3D-printing facilities, two different shapes, such as sandwich- and interdigitated-configurations of ASCs are fabricated. The customized ASCs provide excellent capacitive performance. Such ASCs combining the MXene and electroactive 3D-printed nanocarbon framework can be used as potential energy storage devices in modern electronics.

1. Introduction

The rising advances of portable and wearable electronics demanded the future energy storage devices to become thin, lightweight, and flexible with a customized shape, and safe in use.^[1,2] Among energy storage devices, supercapacitors (SCs) are enticed as an alternative to the battery because of their high power density, high cycle stability, and safe in use.^[3,4] Recently, 2D nanomaterials, analogous to graphene such as transition metal carbides or nitrides (MXenes)^[5-10] and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs)^[11,12] have gained severe attention in the energy storage segments due to their high surface area and high conductivity, high mechanical stability, wide interlayer spacing, and high theoretical capacitance.^[11,13] MXenes have their general formula $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$, where M stands for early transition metal (such as Ti, V, and Mo), X stands for C and/or N, $n = 1, 2, \text{ or } 3$, and T_x represents various surface terminations ($-\text{O}-$, $-\text{OH}$, and/or $-\text{F}$, etc.). MXenes are produced by selective extraction of the "A" element from their parent MAX phases ($M_{n+1}AX_n$),

where A stands for group 13 elements such as Al and Ga.^[14-17] The distinctive structure and surface chemistry render MXenes to provide extraordinary properties such as high mechanical stability, a metallic-like conductivity, hydrophilic surface with edge functional groups such as $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{O}$, and $-\text{F}$.^[18] These superior properties make them a promising candidate in energy storage application.^[19] The MXene based structures with varied geometry have been applied in SCs,^[20,21] Li/Na ion batteries,^[22,23] or Li-S batteries.^[15,19,24] However, the performance of MXenes is hindered by the stacking of 2D layers sheets. Moreover, the low potential window (ΔV) of most of the MXenes based SCs confines to 0.4–0.8 V, which limits their energy density.^[25] The electrochemical performance of the MXenes can be improved taking into account different strategies like generating porous structures or placing interlayer spacers between layered MXene sheets.^[26,27] Apparently, a high energy density SC should possess high specific capacitance and wide ΔV . In this regard, the fabrication of an asymmetric supercapacitor (ASC) can enhance the potential window up to 2 V in the aqueous-based electrolyte.^[28]

Recently, molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) from the family of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) has been identified

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1 as a promising material for energy storage application due to
2 its unique structural properties.^[29,30] In a MoS₂ sheet, the Mo
3 atomic layer is sandwiched by two S-layers. In multilayer MoS₂
4 sheets, the layers are stacked by van der Waals force. As the central
5 Mo atoms possess a wide range of oxidation states of +2 to
6 +6, the MoS₂ leads to promising pseudocapacitive behavior.^[30,31]
7 Recent reports in the energy storage field suggest that the integration
8 of such 2D nanomaterials in the 3D structure such as
9 porous scaffold, film, or networks could solve the generic issue
10 of poor ionic and electronic transport in electrode materials. The
11 3D printing of electrode materials can easily make 3D structures
12 with customized shapes. The porous 3D structure permits
13 easy ions transport and gives a low mass to volume ratio in
14 the same footprint area. Fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D
15 printing has captivated severe attention in recent times in the
16 field of energy storage because to its facile and low-cost printing
17 methods. A commercial conductive filament comprises nano-
18 carbon fibers and polylactic acid (PLA) has become very popular
19 for fabricating electrodes for SCs and batteries.^[32–36] However,
20 the presence of insulating PLA polymer in the filament matrix
21 results in poor electrochemical properties. Different approaches
22 such as conductive coating,^[35] solvent treatment,^[37] NaOH
23 treatment,^[38] thermal treatment,^[39,40] and electrochemical activations^[41]
24 were followed to overcome the poor conductivity of
25 the 3D-printed electrodes (3D-PEs). The thermal activation technique
26 was found to be most effective as it removed most of the
27 PLA from the 3D-PE.^[40] In this study, a 3D-printed nanocarbon
28 framework (3DnCF) electrode comprising of nanocarbon fibers
29 was prepared through 3D printing of nanocarbon/PLA filament
30 followed by thermal activation. To enhance the electrochemical
31 performance of the activated electrode, a coaxial electrochemical
32 coating of MoS_{3-x} was employed on of the nanocarbon fibers.
33 We followed the electrodeposition technique for MoS_{3-x} coating
34 because it is well accepted simple and inexpensive approach
35 as compared to other expensive techniques such as chemical
36 vapor deposition (CVD)^[42,43] which require complex steps and
37 high-cost vacuum technologies. Moreover, the electrodeposition
38 technique is even better than other exfoliation or solution phase
39 methods as it can produce *nano-* to *micrometer* thick films with a
40 controllable thickness.^[44–46]

41 Herein, we fabricated exfoliated Ti₃C₂T_x MXene (Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x)
42 with wrinkled sheets for negative electrode and MoS_{3-x} coated
43 3D-printed nanocarbon framework (MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF) for the
44 positive electrode to construct an ASC utilizing PVA/H₂SO₄ gel
45 electrolyte. The ASC showed a wide operating potential window
46 of 1.6 V. The gel electrolyte provides balanced electrochemical
47 properties and higher mechanical stability, and very safe in
48 use.^[47] Two different configurations, such as a sandwich and an
49 interdigitated configurations of ASCs were fabricated employing
50 the advantages of the 3D-printing facilities, which provide excellent
51 electrochemical performance. This work exploits the use of
52 MXene and electroactive 3D-printed hybrid electrode in customized
53 energy storage devices for real-life applications.

54 55 56 57 2. Results and Discussion

58 The synthesis of Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x negative electrode and
59 MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF positive electrode and their arrangement to

design two different configurations of ASCs are presented by
schematic diagrams as shown in **Figure 1**. We separately characterized
the negative and positive electrodes followed by electrochemical
characterization of the ASC cells.

2.1. Negative Electrode

We synthesized the Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x MXene by etching of Ti₃AlC₂ MAX phase followed by delamination using tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBAOH) as shown in Figure 1a. The surface morphology of the Ti₃AlC₂ and Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x were characterized by the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique. The SEM micrograph of the Ti₃AlC₂ is depicted in **Figure 2a** which shows stacked 2D layers of Ti-Al-C sheets. The Ti₃AlC₂ lost Al layers after etching with hydrofluoric acid (HF) and formed an accordion-like morphology^[48,49] as displayed in Figure 2b. A magnified image is shown in Figure 2c which depicts the 2D layer-by-layer structure of the Ti₃C₂T_x. The delamination of Ti₃C₂T_x yielded a self-assembled 3D structure which was grinded into small flakes as shown in Figure 2d. The SEM image of the exfoliated and delaminated Ti₃C₂T_x (Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x) is shown in Figure 2e which shows that the Ti₃C₂T_x layers are successfully delaminated and appeared as small flakes through the stacking of few Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x sheets. A magnified image in Figure 2f revealed that the exfoliated sheets possess a wrinkled surface. The etching and delamination reactions can be stated by Equations S1–S3 (Supporting Information).^[11,44] To further confirm the exfoliation and delamination process, the high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) was carried out on Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x as depicted in Figure 2g–i. The HR-TEM images show that the Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x MXene flakes are 500 nm to 1 μm in length, and 2 to 4 sheets are stacked together.

Further, the Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x was characterized using energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy operated with SEM to find out the constituent elements and elemental mappings. The SEM-EDX survey spectrum of the Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x is shown in Figure S1a (Supporting Information), which discloses the presence of Ti, C, F, O, and Al elements in the atomic percentage of 39.6%, 18.3%, 21.7%, 19.1%, and 1.2%, respectively. The EDX mapped area and mappings of the constituent elements of Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x are shown in Figure 2j–o. The mappings show the distribution of Ti and C along with F elements. The trace amount of Al can be ascribed by the presence of the Al-based impurity in the sample which is evident from the etching reaction as stated by Equation S1 (Supporting Information).

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) study of the pristine Ti₃AlC₂ and Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x are shown in **Figure 3a**. The Ti₃AlC₂ shows the intense characteristic peaks at 2θ of 9.4° and 39° corresponding to the (002) and (104) planes, respectively. The characteristic (002) plane of Ti₃AlC₂ is shifted from 9.4° to 7.9° in Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x. Moreover, the successful chemical exfoliation and delamination of the Ti₃C₂T_x can be confirmed by a dramatic decrease of peak intensity for (104) plane at 39°.^[14,50] The exfoliation process to obtain Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x sheets results in the decrease in peaks intensity, and the nonplanar sheets further widening the corresponding peaks, as observed by other MXenes exfoliation work.^[14,49] Moreover, the elemental composition and bonding environment of the pristine Ti₃AlC₂ and Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x

Figure 1. Schematic diagrams of a) synthesis of exfoliated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene, b) fabrication of MoS_{3-x} coated 3D-printed nanocarbon framework ($\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}$); c) asymmetric supercapacitors sandwich- and d) interdigitated configurations.

are evaluated using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis. The XPS survey spectra of Ti_3AlC_2 and $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ are shown in Figure 3b. The survey spectrum of Ti_3AlC_2 shows the presence of Ti 2p, C 1s, and Al 2p peaks at 456, 285, and 73 eV, respectively whereas the survey spectrum of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ shows the presence of prominent Ti 2p, C 1s, F 1s, and O 1s peaks. The absence of Al 2p peak in $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ suggests the successful etching of the Al layer from the Ti_3AlC_2 . The prominent presence of F 1s in the $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ suggests the functionalization of F after HF treatment. To comprehend the bonding states of the constituent elements, the high-resolution core-level spectra were analyzed. The core level Ti 2p spectrum of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ (Figure 3c) shows two doublets at 455.5 and 461.5 eV corresponding to Ti 2p_{3/2} and Ti 2p_{1/2}, respectively of the Ti-C carbide bond of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$. There are four-pairs of other peaks located at 456.3/462.0, 457.6/463.3, 459.3/465.0, and 460.5/466.2 eV, corresponding to Ti 2p_{3/2}/Ti 2p_{1/2} states of Ti(II), Ti(III), $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_{2x}$ and TiF_3 , respectively.^[51–54] The core level C 1s spectrum of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ exhibits five peaks located at 282.3, 282.8, 284.3, 285.0, and 285.8 eV corresponding to the C–Ti–F_x, C–TiO_x, C–C (sp²), C–C (sp³), and C–O (adventitious C), respectively as depicted in Figure 3d.^[53] The deconvolution of O 1s spectrum (Figure 3e) displays the peaks at 530.1, 530.9, 532.0, 533.1, and 534.4 eV corresponding to the C–Ti–O_x, $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_{2x}$, C–Ti–OH, C–O (adventitious O) and adsorbed H₂O, respectively.^[53,55,56]

Hereby, the O 1s peaks are corroborated with the C 1s peaks. Besides, the deconvolution of the F 1s spectrum shows the peaks at 685.4 and 686.0 eV corresponding to the C–Ti–F_x and $\text{TiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_{2x}$, respectively (Figure 3f).^[51,56] The peak located at 686.7 eV corroborated with the unidentified fluorinated phase as reported in the literature,^[53] can be ascribed as Ti–F_x. The core level Al 2p spectrum did not show any peaks (Figure 3g) which confirms the successful etching of Al. Based on the deconvolution of high-resolution core-level spectra, the quantification data of the $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{T}_2\text{T}_x$ is reported in Table S1. It is found that the total contribution from the $\text{Ti}_3\text{T}_2\text{T}_x$ phase is 72.26 at% and three types of surface functional groups such as fluoride (–F–), oxide (–O–), and hydroxyl (–OH) are present in $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$.^[51,52]

The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis was carried out to measure the specific surface area (SSA) of the Ti_3AlC_2 and $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ as depicted in Figure S2 (Supporting Information). The $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ shows the SSA of 10.91 m² g^{–1} which is ≈2 times higher than the SSA of Ti_3AlC_2 (5.5 m² g^{–1}). The pore volumes of Ti_3AlC_2 and $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ are calculated to be 0.0256 and 0.0117 cc g^{–1}, respectively.

To carry out the electrochemical measurement, the $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ was pasted on carbon cloth (CC) as described in the Experimental section. The cyclic voltammetry (CV) study was carried out for $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode in 1 M H₂SO₄ using

Figure 2. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of a) Ti_3AlC_2 ; b) etched- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ at lower magnification and c) at higher magnification; d) optical photograph of self-assembled exfoliated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ ($\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$) which is grinded into smaller flakes; e) SEM images of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ at lower magnification and f) higher magnification; g–i) high-resolution transmission electron microscopy images of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$; j) SEM-energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy mapping area, and k–o) EDX mapping of Ti K, C K, F K, O K, and Al K, respectively of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$.

Ag/AgCl (1 M KCl) as reference electrode and Pt as a counter electrode. The cyclic voltammograms show a relatively capacitive potential window at -0.6 to 0 V. The cyclic voltammograms at the scan rates from 25 to 300 mV s^{-1} are shown in Figure 4a. The current was increased with increasing the scan rates in the selected potential window showing a good rate capability of the electrode material. The cyclic voltammograms show distorted rectangular patterns which express that the charge storing mechanism is governed by surface-controlled double-layer capacitive and pseudocapacitive paths.

The galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) measurement was carried out for the $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode at the same potential window of CV measurement from -0.6 to 0 V as depicted in Figure 4b. The charge–discharge profiles are symmetric and display a triangular pattern. This expresses a

dominant double-layer capacitive behavior which is corroborated with the CV study. The variations of areal capacitance and gravimetric capacitance with current density are depicted in Figure 4c. The $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode shows the areal capacitance of 90 mF cm^{-2} at a current density of 1 mA cm^{-2} and gravimetric capacitance of 90 F g^{-1} at a specific current of 1 A g^{-1} . The high capacitance value can be attributed to the high conductivity and high surface area of the wrinkled $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$.

To evaluate the impedance behavior of the $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode, the Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) study was carried out in a wide range of frequencies from 100 kHz to 0.01 Hz applying an alternating current of 10 mV. The Nyquist and Bode plots from the EIS study are depicted in Figure 4d,e, respectively. The fitted circuit diagram of the Nyquist plot is shown as an inset in Figure 4d. The R_s

Figure 3. a) X-ray diffraction patterns of the pristine Ti_3AlC_2 and $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$; X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy b) survey spectra of Ti_3AlC_2 and $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$, high-resolution core-level spectra of c) Ti 2p, d) C 1s, e) O 1s, f) F 1s, and g) Al 2p of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$.

represents the equivalent series resistance which includes the intrinsic resistance of the electrode material, interfacial resistance between the electrode material and current collector, and the interfacial resistance between electrode material and electrolyte. The R_s was found to be 2.7Ω . Such a low R_s is due to the low solution resistance and low intrinsic resistance of the electrode material. The charge transfer resistance, R_{ct} which is originated from the charge transfer reaction at the electrode-electrolyte interface is determined from the semicircle of the Nyquist plot at the high-frequency region. The R_{ct} was found to be $189 \text{ m}\Omega$. The low R_{ct} value can be ascribed to the high conductivity of the $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$. The inclined part at the post semicircle region determines the diffusion resistance from the bulk of electrolyte to the electrode, which is also known as Warburg resistance, W_d . The slope of the straight line determines the W_d . When the inclined line is parallel to the Y-axis, it states an ideal double-layer capacitive behavior. Here, the inclined line presents a real supercapacitor behavior where charge storage is controlled by surface-controlled electrochemical double layer (EDL) capacitive and pseudocapacitive mechanisms. The constant phase element (CPE) elucidates the deviation of SC from ideal SC. The impedance (Z) is related to CPE (Y_0) by the Equation (1)^[57]

$$Z = (Y_0 j\omega)^{-n} \quad (1)$$

where, ω is the angular frequency. The power factor n diverges as $0 < n < 1$. The n value closer to 1 indicates ideal EDL-type capacitive behavior. The $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode shows a CPE of 3.75 mS s^n ,

where $n = 0.71$. The n value reveals that the charge storage is controlled by dominative EDL-type capacitive behavior. The Bode plot in Figure 4f depicts the variation of impedance and phase angle with frequency. It is well-known that a phase angle of -90° represents ideal capacitive behavior, while a phase angle of -90° to -45° represents a primarily capacitive behavior and a phase angle of -45° to 0° represents mostly diffusion-controlled capacitive and resistive behavior.^[58] In this study, the phase angle reaches a maximum at an angle of -84.4° which illustrates surface-controlled capacitive behavior as also evident from the CV study and Nyquist plot.^[59] The real (C') and imaginary capacitances (C'') were calculated using Equations S9 and S10 in the Supporting Information, respectively from the measured impedance of the Bode plot. The C'' versus frequency plot is depicted in Figure 4f. It was found that a maximum C'' of 28.5 mF cm^{-2} was found at the frequency of 0.630 Hz . The dielectric relaxation time (τ_0), which was determined using Equation (2), where f_0 is the frequency at the point of maximum C'' ^[60]

$$\tau_0 = 1/f_0 \quad (2)$$

The τ_0 was calculated to be 1.59 s when a maximum C'' was reached.

2.2. Positive Electrode

The positive electrode was fabricated via 3D printing of nano-carbon/PLA filament with defined shapes (Figure S3, Supporting

Figure 4. a) Cyclic voltammogram study at different scan rates, b) galvanostatic charge–discharge at different current densities, c) the variation of areal and gravimetric capacitances with current density, d) Nyquist plot with the fitted line, inset: magnified plot at higher frequency range and the fitted circuit model, e) Bode plot showing the variation of impedance and phase angle with frequency, f) variation of imaginary and real capacitances with frequency from the Bode plot of Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x/CC electrode.

Information) followed by electrodeposition of MoS_{3-x} on the thermally activated 3D-printed electrode (Figure S4, Supporting Information). The optical photographs of the 3D-printed nanocarbon/PLA (3DnC/PLA) electrodes, thermally activated 3D-printed nanocarbon frameworks (3DnCFs) and MoS_{3-x} coated 3DnCFs (MoS_{3-x}@3DnCFs) pasted on CCs (MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CCs) are shown in Figure 5a–c, respectively. The thermal activation of 3DnC/PLA electrodes at 350 °C removes the PLA from the matrix, which is also evident from the thermogravimetric analysis and other electrochemical studies employing the exact filament.^[32,36,40] Interestingly, the 3DnC/PLA electrodes retain similar shapes even after the thermal activation. The SEM morphology of the 3DnC electrode shows that it is made of nanocarbon fibers which are encapsulated by PLA (Figure 5d). After thermal activation, the activated electrode (3DnCF) shows porous framework which is comprised with a network of nanocarbon fibers of diameters about 110–140 nm and lengths of few microns (Figure 5e). The nanocarbon fibers remain as an entangled network that aids the 3DnCF to keep its original shape of 3DnC/PLA. However, due to the removal of PLA from the matrix of the 3DnCF, the dimension of the electrode shrinks about 5%. The SEM image of the MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF shows a uniform coating of MoS_{3-x} on the nanocarbon fibers, where the coated fibers have diameters of 180–280 nm as observed from Figure 5f. Thus, the difference of diameter of 3DnCF and MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF shows a coating thickness of 35–70 nm. To confirm the coating of MoS_{3-x} on nanocarbon fibers, the EDX study was carried out on the MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF. The EDX spectrum analysis shows

the presence of Mo, S, C, O, and Ti with atomic percentages of 10.69%, 38.30%, 28.93%, 21.91%, 0.67% as depicted in Figure S1b (Supporting Information). Moreover, the EDX mapping of Mo L and S K (Figure 5h,i) confirm the coaxial coating of MoS_{3-x} on the 3DnCF surface. The occurrence of a trace amount of Ti in the MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF endorse the presence of the inherent impurity in the filament as reported in the literature^[36,40,61]

To further confirm the elemental compositions and bonding states of the coated MoS_{3-x} layer, the XPS study was carried out. The survey spectrum of the 3DnCF and MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF are displayed in Figure 6a. The atomic percentages of the constituent elements are shown in the inset table of Figure 6a which indicates that the ratio of Mo and S in MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF is ≈1:3. The deconvolution of Mo 3d spectra (Figure 6b) shows a pair of peaks at 229.83 and 232.98 eV keeping a spin-orbit peak separation of 3.15 eV, corresponding to the Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{3/2} and Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{5/2} states of MoS₂, respectively. Another pair of peaks located at 230.43 and 233.58 eV are corresponding to Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{5/2} and Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{3/2}, respectively, which can be ascribed to the formation of a trace amount of MoO₂. The ratio of peak intensity for Mo(IV) S₂ to Mo(IV)O₂ was found to be 1:0.51. Besides, the intense peaks located at 232.77 and 235.92 eV which are corresponding to the Mo⁶⁺ 3d_{5/2} and Mo⁶⁺ 3d_{3/2} oxidation states, respectively, are assigned to the formation of MoS₃. The peak at 228 eV is corresponding to the S 2s. The peak intensity ratio of Mo(IV) S₂ to Mo(VI)S₃ was found to be 1:0.67. The core-level spectrum of S 2p is depicted in Figure 6c. The peaks located at 162.48 and 163.64 eV are corresponding to the S²⁻ 2p_{3/2} and S²⁻ 2p_{1/2},

Figure 5. Optical photographs of a) 3D-printed nanocarbon/PLA electrode, b) thermally activated 3D-printed nanocarbon framework, and c) MoS_{3-x} coated 3D-printed nanocarbon framework (MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF); d–f) Their corresponding scanning electron micrographs; energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy: g) map area, and mapping of h) Mo L and i) S K of MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF.

Figure 6. a) X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy: survey spectra of 3D-printed nanocarbon framework (3DnCF) and MoS_{3-x} coated 3DnCF (MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF), high resolution core level spectra of b) Mo 3d, c) S 2p, d) O 1s, and e) Ti 2p of MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF; f) X-ray diffraction of 3DnCF and MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF.

1 respectively, acquainting a spin-orbit peak separation of 1.16 eV.
2 Besides, another pair of peaks located at 163.96 and 165.12 eV
3 can be attributed to the bridging S_2^{2-} bonding state of the S_3
4 ligand. The ratio of S^{2-} to S_2^{2-} was found to be 1:2. Relating the
5 ratio $Mo(IV)S_2$ to $Mo(VI)S_3$ and the ratio of S^{2-} to S_2^{2-} , we can
6 say that the sample contains a mixed phase of MoS_2 and MoS_3 .
7 Thus, the obtained molybdenum sulfides with mixed phases are
8 formulated as MoS_{3-x} , where $0 \leq x \leq 1$. The formation of MoS_2
9 and MoS_3 phases can be explained by Equations (3) and (4),
10 respectively.^[45,46,62,63]

16 In anodic process, the precursor $[MoS_4]^{2-}$ is reduced to MoS_2
17 (Equation (3))^[45,46] and in cathodic process, the precursor is
18 converted to MoS_3 through the oxidation of sulfur ligand fol-
19 lowing by an intramolecular electron transfer to the Mo atom
20 and then loss of S atom (Equation (4)).^[62,63] The deconvolution
21 of O 1s spectrum (Figure 6d) confirms the presence of metal
22 oxide peak which once again supports the formation of MoO_2 .
23 The deconvolution of Ti 2p (Figure 6e) shows a pair of peaks
24 located at 455 and 465 eV corresponding to the $Ti^{4+} 2p_{3/2}$ and
25 $Ti^{4+} 2p_{1/2}$, respectively, which are ascribed to the inherent TiO_2
26 impurity in the filament.^[36,40,61]

27 Further to confirm the crystalline nature of the MoS_{3-x}
28 coating, the XRD analysis was carried out for 3DnCF and
29 $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$ as shown in Figure 6f. However, no obvious
30 peaks were observed from the MoS_{3-x} structure. This can
31 be attributed to the amorphous morphology of the MoS_{3-x}
32 phase which is typically formed during electrochemical
33 deposition.^[40,48]

34 The electrochemical behavior of the $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$
35 electrodes was analyzed using CV in the three-electrode test
36 setup in 1 M H_2SO_4 electrolyte. The CV measurement was car-
37 ried out within a potential window of 0–1.0 V at the scan rates
38 from 25 to 300 $mV s^{-1}$ as shown in Figure 7a. The cyclic voltam-
39 mograms show two prominent peaks during the anodic and
40 cathodic sweeps over all the scan rates. Moreover, the current
41 increases with increasing the scan rates which reveals a good
42 rate capability of the $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$. The CV study of the
43 blank 3DnCF/CC electrode Figure S5a (Supporting Informa-
44 tion) was carried out at the same potential window with same
45 experimental conditions. The cyclic voltammograms of the
46 blank 3DnCF/CC and $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$ are compared at the
47 scan rate of 100 $mV s^{-1}$ as depicted in Figure 7b. Interestingly,
48 both the electrodes show two prominent peaks corresponding
49 to the cathodic and anodic redox reactions. However, the peak
50 intensity was increased for $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$ electrode.
51 For the blank 3DnCF/CC electrode, the anodic and cathodic
52 peaks located at 0.52 and 0.34 V, respectively at a scan rate
53 of 100 $mV s^{-1}$, are resulted from the inherent impurities and
54 surface functional groups of the nanocarbon fibers.^[34] In the
55 case of $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$, the coaxial coating of MoS_{3-x} on
56 the nanocarbon fibers influences the charge–discharge mech-
57 anism of the electrode which is evident from the broadening
58 and enhancement of the cathodic and anodic peak intensities
59 as observed in Figure 7b. A comparison of areal capacitances

between blank 3DnCF/CC and the $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$ 1
electrodes for scan rates of 25–100 $mV s^{-1}$ is depicted in 2
Figure S5b (Supporting Information). It was found that the 3
 $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$ shows 1.53 times higher capacitance 4
than 3DnCF/CC at scan rate of 100 $mV s^{-1}$. However, it shows 5
1.64 times of higher capacitance at lower scan rate of 6
25 $mV s^{-1}$ due to slower ions insertion-deinsertion. The incre- 7
ment of capacitance in $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$ can be attributed 8
to the surface adsorption-desorption and intercalation-deinter- 9
calation reaction by MoS_{3-x} . The possible pseudocapacitive 10
reactions by MoS_{3-x} and inherent impurity (TiO_2) can be stated 11
by Equations (5–7).^[55,56,64]

20 To comprehend the charge storage mechanisms, the kinetics
21 was studied following Dunn and co-workers approach as stated
22 in Equation (8).^[65]

$$23 i = av^b \quad (8)$$

26 where, i is the peak current, v is the scan rate, and a and b are
27 variables. When the value of b is equal to 1 signifies the charge
28 storage mechanism is surface-controlled and the b value of
29 0.5 signifies diffusion-controlled battery-like pseudocapacitive
30 reaction.^[65–67] Using Equation (8), $\log i$ against $\log v$ can be
31 plotted to determine the value of b for both cathodic and anodic
32 peaks (Figure 7c). Here, the b values for the anodic and cathodic
33 process are found to be 0.654 and 0.658, respectively. The simi-
34 lar b value in cathodic and anodic process confirms that redox
35 reactions are highly reversible.^[68] These values indicate that
36 the charge storage here controlled by both surface- and diffusion-
37 controlled paths. Thus the stored charge can be divided into
38 two parts following the approach by Dunn and co-workers^[69] as
39 stated in Equation (9).

$$41 i(V) = k_1v + k_2 v^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

43 where, v is scan rate. k_1 and k_2 are the constants. Here, k_1v rep-
44 represents the capacitive process and $k_2v^{1/2}$ battery-like diffusion-
45 controlled process. The Equation (9) can be reshuffled into
46 Equation (10)

$$48 \frac{i(V)}{v^{1/2}} = k_1v^{1/2} + k_2 \quad (10)$$

51 By plotting $i(V)/v^{1/2}$ versus $v^{1/2}$, the k_1 and k_2 , and corre-
52 sponding k_1v and $k_2v^{1/2}$ values can be determined.^[70] The current
53 was then separated into surface-controlled and diffusion-
54 controlled parts as shown in Figure 7d. The non-shaded area
55 represents the charge storing following diffusion-controlled
56 intercalation type pseudocapacitive path which is equal to 26%
57 of total charge at the scan rate of 50 $mV s^{-1}$. The percentage of
58 charge separation into surface- and diffusion-controlled paths at
59 different scan rates are shown in Figure 7e, which shows that at

Figure 7. a) Cyclic voltammetry (CV) study at different scan rates of $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ electrode, b) comparison of CV between $3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ and $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ at the scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} , c) $\log(\text{peak current density} [\text{mA cm}^{-2}])$ versus $\log(\text{scan rate} [\text{mV s}^{-1}])$ plot to determine the b values for anodic and cathodic processes, d) separation of current-voltage plot into diffusion- and capacitive-controlled at the scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} . e) The separation of the percentage of stored charge into diffusion- and capacitive-controlled contributions for 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, and 200 mV s^{-1} . f) Galvanostatic charge-discharge at different constant current densities. g) Nyquist plot with fitting, inset: magnified plot at higher frequency range and fitted circuit model. h) Bode plot showing the variation of impedance and phase angle with frequency. i) Variation of imaginary and real capacitances with the frequency of $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ electrode.

higher scans surface-controlled capacitance enhanced due to fast diffusions of ions from and into the electrode to the electrolyte.

Further, the GCD measurements of the $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ electrode at different current densities are plotted in Figure 7f. The charge-discharge patterns show hump/shoulder regions which can be ascribed to the pseudocapacitive charge storage mechanism as explained in the CV study. The $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ electrode shows the areal capacitance of 975, 90.0, 85.0, and 80 mF cm^{-2} at the constant current densities of 0.5, 2.5, 5.0, and 10 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. The high areal capacitance at low current suggests that slower ion insertion de-insertion at low current enables the access of higher active surface area which increases the capacitance.

The EIS study was carried out for the $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ electrode within a frequency range of 100 kHz to 0.01 Hz

applying an alternating current of 10 mV. The Nyquist plot from the EIS study are shown in Figure 7g. The fitted circuit model is shown as an inset in Figure 7g. The R_s and R_{ct} were found to be 2.21 and 0.109 Ω , respectively. The lower intrinsic resistance of the $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}$ and low solution resistance ensued low R_s value. The porous nanocarbon network facilitates faster charge transfer to the electrode which resulted in a lower R_{ct} value. The Bode plot in Figure 7h shows the variation of phase angle and impedance with the frequency. The phase angle versus frequency plot shows that the electrode obtains a high phase angle of -76.33° . This indicates that the charge stored in a combination of both EDL and pseudocapacitive paths as explained in the previous section. The C' and C'' were derived using Equations S9 and S10 in the Supporting Information, respectively, and the corresponding C'' versus frequency

Figure 8. a) Cyclic voltammetry (CV) study of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ and $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ electrodes in three-electrode test system at 100 mV s^{-1} , b) CV study of the sandwich configuration solid-state asymmetric supercapacitor (SS-ASC) with increasing potential window from 0–1.0 to 0–1.6 V, c) CV study at the potential window of 1.6 V with different scan rates, d) galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) study at different current densities, e) variation of areal and volumetric capacitances with current densities, f) Ragone plot, comparison with reported data, g) cyclic stability and Coulombic efficiency study for 25 000 cycles, inset: schematic of ions transfer towards positive and negative electrodes, h) GCD study of one, two- and three-series connected SS-ASC cells, inset: photograph of one green-LED lightening by three-series-connected cells, and i) photographs of two red-LEDs, and one green- and one red-LEDs lightening by three-series-connected cells.

plot is depicted in Figure 7i. The C'' shows a maximum value at the frequency 0.398 Hz. Using Equation (2), the relaxation time, τ_0 was calculated to be 2.51 s when the C'' was reached at maximum value.

2.3. Solid-State Asymmetric Supercapacitor (SS-ASC)

From the previous measurements of the positive and negative electrodes in the three-electrode test system, it is evident that the $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ shows the capacitive potential window from 0 to -0.6 V ($\Delta V = 0.6 \text{ V}$) while the $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}$ shows a window from 0 to $+1.0 \text{ V}$ ($\Delta V = 1.0 \text{ V}$) as shown in Figure 8a. Seemingly, the ASC comprising of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{CC}$ as negative electrode and $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DnCF}/\text{CC}$ as positive electrode can reach

a potential window of 1.6 V. Before fabricating the ASC, it is essential to optimize the charges stored in the positive and negative electrodes following Equation (11)^[28]

$$\frac{m_+}{m_-} = \frac{C_- \Delta V_-}{C_+ \Delta V_+} \quad (11)$$

where, C_- and C_+ are the gravimetric capacitances of the negative and positive electrodes, respectively, ΔV_- and ΔV_+ are the potential windows of the negative and positive electrodes, respectively, and m_- and m_+ are the mass of the active materials of negative and positive electrodes, respectively. From the CV measurements, the positive electrode, $\text{MoS}_{3-x}@3\text{DPE}/\text{CC}$ shows gravimetric capacitance of 5.25 F g^{-1} and the negative electrode $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ shows the gravimetric capacitance

1 of 96.72 F g⁻¹ at scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. Equalling the stored
2 charge in the respective electrodes, the mass ratio of the posi-
3 tive to negative electrode materials was found to be 11:1. Fol-
4 lowing the mass ratio, the SS-ASC was fabricated utilizing the
5 PVA/H₂SO₄ gel electrolyte. A schematic diagram of the fabrica-
6 tion of sandwich configuration SS-ASC is shown in Figure S6a
7 (Supporting Information). The potential window of the SS-ASC
8 was optimized by gradual increasing the potential limits from
9 0–1.0 to 0–1.8 V. The cyclic voltammograms of the SS-ASC for
10 the potential windows of 0–1.0, 0–1.2, 0–1.4, 0–1.6, and 0–1.8 V
11 at the scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹ are shown in Figure 8b. Appar-
12 ently, it was found that the SS-ASC shows a stable potential
13 window of 0–1.6 V which is as obvious from the potential range
14 studied in the three-electrode test system. Thus, the CV study
15 of the SS-ASC was carried out with increasing scan rates from
16 25 to 300 mV s⁻¹ at the potential window of 0–1.6 V as depicted
17 in Figure 8c. The cyclic voltammograms remained stables
18 over the chosen scan rates. The current density increased with
19 increasing the scan rates that proofs a good rate capability of
20 the SS-ASC device.

21 The cyclic voltammogram shows small anodic and cathodic
22 peaks at the potentials of 0.61 and 0.42 V, respectively at the
23 scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. It was found that the positions of the
24 anodic and cathodic peaks were shifted with the scan rates.
25 The peaks are seeming to be from the MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF posi-
26 tive electrode as explained in the previous section. Although the
27 peak intensity was decreased as compared to the peak obtained
28 in the three-electrode system using the 1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte.
29 This is obvious from the ionic mobility difference between the
30 aqueous and gel electrolyte.

31 The galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) measurement
32 was carried out within the same potential window of 0–1.6 V
33 at current densities of 0.25, 0.5, 1.5, 2.5, 5.0, and 7.5 mA cm⁻²
34 as depicted in Figure 8d. It was found that the GCD patterns
35 are symmetric in nature displaying a slight hump at the poten-
36 tial range of 0.2–0.6 V. This is analogous to the small peaks
37 observed in the CV study. The SS-ASC cell shows a high
38 areal capacitance of 160 mF cm⁻² at the current density of
39 0.25 mA cm⁻² and volumetric capacitance of 106770 mF cm⁻³
40 at the current density of 1.66 mA cm⁻³. The high areal and volu-
41 metric capacitances (including current collector) of the SS-ASC
42 can be enlightened by the high capacitive behavior from Ex-
43 Ti₃C₂T_x MXene and 3D porous MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF at the wide
44 potential window of 1.6 V. The variation of areal and volumetric
45 capacitances with the variation of current density is shown
46 in Figure 8e which shows increasing trend of capacitances at
47 lower current densities. The electrolyte ions can get sufficient
48 time at lower current density to enter slowly deep inside of the
49 exfoliated and porous electrodes, which causes an increasing
50 trend of capacitance at lower current densities. To understand
51 the relationship between energy density and power density, the
52 Ragone chart is plotted as depicted in Figure 8f. The SS-ASC
53 cell shows the areal energy density of 56.94 μWh cm⁻² at a areal
54 power density of 0.20 mW cm⁻². Interestingly, the SS-ASC
55 cell keeps its high energy density of 23.33 μWh cm⁻² even at
56 a high power density of 6.00 mW cm⁻². Comparisons of the
57 energy density versus power density of MXene based solid-
58 state SCs from reported data^[13,71–76] are shown in Figure 8f.
59 These results suggest that the as-fabricated SS-ASC shows

comparable or high performance to other MXene based solid- 1
state SCs. Besides, the volumetric and gravimetric capacitances, 2
and corresponding energy and power densities of the SS-ASC 3
are reported in Table S2. The cyclic stability of the SS-ASC 4
was measured through GCD measurement for 25 000 cycles at the 5
constant current density of 7.5 mA cm⁻² as shown in Figure 8g. 6
It was found that the capacitance was increased to 114% of initial 7
capacitance till 8000 cycles and remained constant until 8
19 000 cycles. Afterwards, the capacitance was decreased and 9
reached back to 100% after 23 500 cycles and then further 10
decreased. A capacitance retention of 92.8% was observed after 11
25 000 cycles. Such long-run outstanding cyclic stability of the 12
SS-ASC can be attributed to the morphology and mechanical 13
stability of the porous 3D-printed nanocarbon framework and 14
exfoliated Ti₃C₂T_x sheets toward electrochemical charge–dis- 15
charge phenomena. The porous 3D-printed framework allows 16
the diffusion of electrolyte ions into the bulk of the electrode 17
(Figure 8g, inset) with increasing cycles, which causes the 18
capacitance to increase until 8000 cycles. After 8000 cycles, the 19
whole bulk areas of the electrodes are exploited for charge– 20
discharge and thus the capacitance remained constant up to 21
19 000 cycles. The capacitance was decayed to 92.8% of the initial 22
capacitance after 25 000 cycles. The Coulombic efficiency 23
(CE) was measured throughout the 25 000 cycles of cyclic sta- 24
bility test as depicted in Figure 8g. The ASC shows a excellent 25
rate performance keeping 100% of CE till 22 000 cycles. The 26
CE was decreased to 94% after 25 000 cycles. The degradation 27
trend of CE is similar with cyclic stability result. 28

29 The performance of the SS-ASC was validated by connecting
30 two- and three SS-ASC cells in a series which can be charged
31 up to 3.2 and 4.8 V, respectively. The GCD profiles of the two-,
32 and three-SS-ASC cells connected in series are compared with
33 single-cell at the current density of 5 mA cm⁻² as shown in
34 Figure 8h. Two- and three series-connected SS-ASC cells take
35 similar charging/discharging times corresponding single cell.
36 Three series-connected cells lit up one green-LED (1.8 V) for
37 2 min when it was rapidly charged for 10 s at the current den-
38 sity of 10 mA cm⁻². The photographs of the LEDs lightening
39 for two red-LEDs (1.6 V), and 1 red- and 1 green-LEDs by three
40 series-connected SS-ASC cells are shown in Figure 8i. The cells
41 were charged for 10 s to light up the two series-connected LEDs
42 for ≈60 s. Moreover, a demonstration video file is included in
43 Supporting Video SV1.

44 Moreover, we fabricated the interdigitated SS-ASC
45 comprising of Ex-Ti₃C₂T_x as the negative electrode and
46 MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF as the positive electrode as depicted in
47 **Figure 9a** inset. The CV and GCD measurements of the inter-
48 digitated shaped SS-ASC are shown in Figure 9a,b. The results
49 are analogous with the result obtained in sandwich configura-
50 tion SS-ASC. The interdigitated SS-ASC cell showed the
51 areal capacitance of 55.60 mF cm⁻² at the current density of
52 0.26 mA cm⁻² and volumetric capacitance of 556.09 mF cm⁻³
53 at the current density of 2.60 mA cm⁻³. The variation of areal
54 and volumetric capacitances with current density is shown in
55 Figure 9c which shows typical increasing trend of capacitance
56 at lower current density. The interdigitated SS-ASCs are user-
57 friendly to use. It can be placed even on a lab coat (Figure 9c,
58 inset) to charge the wearable devices. The charge–discharge
59 profile of the series-connected two- and three-cells are shown in

Figure 9. a) Cyclic voltammogram study of interdigitated solid-state asymmetric supercapacitor (SS-ASC), inset: schematic presentation of interdigitated solid-state asymmetric supercapacitor (SS-ASC) comprising of $\text{Ex-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ as the negative electrode and $\text{MoS}_{3-x}/\text{3DnCF}$ as the positive electrode, b) galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) study, c) variation of areal and volumetric capacitances with current density, inset: showing the SS-ASC can be attached with a lab coat, and d) GCD study of one, two- and three-cells connected in series, inset: photographs of the series connection of three SS-ASC cells and lightening up of two-red-LEDs connected in series.

Figure 9d, which showed the two- and three- SS-ASC cells connected in series can reach the potential of 3.2 and 4.8 V, respectively in ≈ 20 s at an applied current density of 1.30 mA cm^{-2} . The three series-connected SS-ASC cells that can lit up one red-LED for 1 min 40 s are shown in Figure 9d inset. The series-connected cells can be used in other electronics applications.

3. Conclusions

The study shows the fabrication of exfoliated- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene flakes with wrinkle surface through delamination and exfoliation of etched MAX phase, and MoS_{3-x} coated 3D porous nanocarbon framework following facile 3D printing and electrodeposition techniques. The exfoliated- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene shows a high gravimetric capacitance of 90 F g^{-1} at the current density of 1 A g^{-1} . The 3D porous framework of the activated nanocarbon electrode provides a large electrochemically active surface area. The electrodeposition of MoS_{3-x} on the nanocarbon framework enhances the overall capacitance through the surface-controlled and diffusion-controlled charge storing mechanism. The asymmetric combination of exfoliated- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ and MoS_{3-x} coated 3D porous nanocarbon framework can reach a potential window of 1.6 V. Exploiting the advantages of the 3D printing, different customized shapes of supercapacitors can be fabricated easily

for use in modern electronics. The sandwich configuration SS-ASC showed a areal capacitance of 160 mF cm^{-2} at the current density was 0.5 mA cm^{-2} . Remarkably, the SS-ASC cell performed excellent capacitive performance till 25 000 cycles. Moreover, the series combination of three-ASC cell lit up a green-LED (1.8 V) for 2 minutes by rapid charging of 10 s. This work can be extended to develop different customized-shaped supercapacitors to fulfill the modern demand for complex-shaped electronics.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: The ammonium tetrathiomolybdate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{MoS}_4$ and PVA (MW 85 000–124 000), potassium bromide (KBr), Nafion 117 solution were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Germany. The titanium powder, aluminum powder, tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBAOH), hydrofluoric acid (HF, 40%), and conductive carbon black (super P) were procured from Alfa-Aesar, Germany. The potassium chloride (KCl), N, N dimethylformamide (DMF), and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 96%) were purchased from Penta, Czech Republic. The conductive carbon cloth was obtained from the Fuel cell store, USA. The graphene/poly(lactic acid) filament (BlackMagic3D) was purchased from Graphene Laboratories Inc., New York, USA. The carbon paste was obtained from Micro to Nano, Netherlands. All the purchased chemicals were of analytical grade. The de-ionized (DI) water was used for all solution preparation owing to a resistivity of $>18 \text{ M}\Omega$.

1 *Synthesis of Exfoliated $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene:* The exfoliated $Ti_3C_2T_x$ was
2 synthesized following a previously reported procedure by the group.^[77,78]
3 The procedure was consisting of three steps; firstly, synthesis of
4 Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase, and next etching of Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase, and finally
5 delamination of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene. In short, to prepare the Ti_3AlC_2 MAX
6 phase, the titanium (3 M, -325 mesh), aluminum (1.2 M, -325 mesh) and
7 graphite (2 M, 2 μ m) powders were ball milled (zirconia balls, diameter
8 = 5 mm) in stoichiometric molar ratio for 24 h in KBr melt with ethanol.
9 For sintering, the reaction mixture was heated in a furnace to 1300 °C
10 at a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ under argon atmosphere and kept for
11 1 h at 1300 °C. After cooling, the Ti_3AlC_2 was isolated from the mixture
12 by dissolving the KBr in hot water followed by rinsing with ethanol and
13 dried in an electric oven at 70 °C for 6 h. To etch the Al layers from the
14 MAX phase, 1 g of Ti_3AlC_2 powder was immersed in 50 mL of HF (40
15 wt%) and continuously stirred for 7 days. The mixture was washed with
16 water and filtered to obtain the etched- $Ti_3C_2T_x$. The etched sample was
17 further delaminated by treating 500 mg etched- $Ti_3C_2T_x$ with 25 mL of
18 40% TBAOH at room temperature for 12 h. The resultant mixture was
19 ultrasonicated for 30 min. The final delaminated $Ti_3C_2T_x$ was separated
20 by centrifuging while washing with DI water several times and dried in a
21 vacuum oven at 50 °C for 24 h. The exfoliated and delaminated sample
22 is denoted as Ex- $Ti_3C_2T_x$ in the following sections.

23 *Fabrication of MoS_{3-x} Coated 3D-Printed Nanocarbon Framework:* The
24 MoS_{3-x} coated 3D-printed nanocarbon framework ($MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$)
25 was fabricated in two steps. In the first step, the nanocarbon electrodes
26 were 3D-printed and thermally activated, and in the second step, MoS_{3-x}
27 was electrochemically coated on the activated nanocarbon electrode
28 surface. For 3D printing, the nanocarbon electrodes were designed using
29 Autodesk Fusion Lab 360 software. The designed electrodes are shown
30 in Figure S3 (Supporting Information). The electrodes were 3D-printed
31 using Prusa 3D Printer (Prusa i3 MK3S, Czech Republic) with a nozzle
32 diameter of 0.6 mm employing the commercial graphene/PLA filament,
33 where the nozzle temperature was set at 215 °C, and the bed temperature
34 was kept at 60 °C. The layer thickness of the electrodes was set for
35 0.15 mm. The 3D-printed nanocarbon/PLA (3DnCF/PLA) electrodes were
36 thermally activated by placing them in a furnace at a temperature of
37 350 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ for 3 h. After the heat treatment,
38 the electrodes were cooled naturally to room temperature. The activated
39 electrode are denoted as 3DnCFs.

40 For the electrochemical coating of MoS_{3-x} , the 3DnCFs were pasted on
41 carbon cloths (CC) of similar shapes as shown in Figure S4 (Supporting
42 Information) employing the carbon paste. The opposite side of the
43 carbon fabric was covered by a scotch tape to prevent electrodeposition
44 on that side. The MoS_{3-x} was coated on the 3DnCF surface in a three-
45 electrode test set-up where 3DnCF/CC was used as working electrode,
46 Ag/AgCl (1 M KCl) as a reference electrode, and Pt wire as the counter
47 electrode in 0.01 M $(NH_4)_2MoS_4$ with 0.1 M KCl electrolyte. The
48 electrodeposition was carried out via cyclic voltammetry (CV) from
49 -1.3 to +0.6 V at the scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ for 25 cycles following the
50 previous work.^[34,79] After MoS_{3-x} deposition, the electrodes were rinsed
51 with DI water and dried in an electric oven at 60 °C for 6 h. The MoS_{3-x}
52 coated nanocarbon framework is denoted as $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$, and the
53 whole electrode with carbon cloth is denoted as $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$.

54 *Fabrication of Solid-State Asymmetric Supercapacitor (SS-ASC):* The
55 SS-ASC cell was fabricated using $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$ as the positive
56 electrode and Ex- $Ti_3C_2T_x$ as the negative electrode materials. After
57 balancing the stored charge between the positive and negative electrodes
58 following Equation (11), it was found that mass ratio of positive to
59 negative electrode was 11:3. After electrodeposition of MoS_{3-x} on the
3DnCF, the mass of $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$ positive electrode was measured
to be 32.24 mg. Thus, the required mass of the negative electrode was
calculated to be 2.93 mg. To fabricate the negative electrode, at first,
a slurry was prepared by mixing the Ex- $Ti_3C_2T_x$ and super P in a 90:10
weight ratio with 1.5 wt% of Nafion 117 solution to reach a total mass
of 2.93 mg. The slurry was then pasted on the CC of (2 cm × 1 cm)
area. The Ex- $Ti_3C_2T_x$ coated CC electrode is denoted as Ex- $Ti_3C_2T_x/CC$.
To fabricate the layer-by-layer sandwich configuration, the PVA/ H_2SO_4
gel electrolyte was applied on the $Ti_3C_2T_x/CC$ and $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$

1 electrodes to make a thin layer of electrolyte on top electrodes. When
2 the gel became semi-solid, the two electrodes were assembled face-to-
3 face adding a separator (whatman filter paper) to obtain a layer-by-layer
4 sandwich configuration SS-ASC cell as shown in Figure S6a (Supporting
5 Information). The PVA/ H_2SO_4 gel electrolyte was prepared following
6 slightly modified version literature data.^[80] Briefly, 4 g of PVA was
7 dissolved in 40 mL H_2O by heating it at 90 °C until the solution became
8 clear. Next, 4 g (2.27 mL) of concentrated H_2SO_4 was added dropwise
9 into the PVA gel and stirred continuously. The PVA/ H_2SO_4 solution was
10 then cooled to room temperature and stored in a glass vial.

11 For the preparation of the interdigitated configuration of ASC, the
12 3DnCF was printed as per the shape of interdigitated electrode as shown
13 in Figure S6b (Supporting Information) and electrochemically coated
14 with MoS_{3-x} following the procedure as mentioned in the previous
15 section. The thickness of the interdigitated shape 3D-PE was fixed
16 from the its design. After electrodeposition of MoS_{3-x} on the 3DnCF,
17 the total thickness of $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$ was calculated to be 0.6 mm
18 (considering the ≈0.07 mm shrinkage of thickness of the 3D-printed
19 electrode after thermal activation), and the mass of the $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF$
20 positive electrode was measured to be 18.32 mg. From the charge
21 balance equation, the mass of the negative electrode was calculated
22 to be 1.66 mg. The CC was cut into a shape of the interdigitated
23 configuration and coated with the slurry comprising of $Ti_3C_2T_x$, super
24 P, Nafion 117 following the same ratio described for sandwiched-
25 shaped configuration. Arranging the positive and negative electrodes
26 as interdigitated configuration in an open 3D-printed PLA box, the PVA/
27 H_2SO_4 gel was applied on top it as depicted in Figure S6b (Supporting
28 Information). When the gel became solidified, the interdigitated SS-ASC
29 cell was taken out from the PLA box and measured for electrochemical
30 characterization. It is noteworthy to mention here that, no external
31 separator was used in between the positive and negative electrodes. The
32 gel electrolyte itself acted as the separator.

33 *Materials Characterization:* The SEM imaging was carried out using
34 FEI VERIOS 460L. The elemental mapping was performed with an EDX
35 detector (EDAX SDD Octane Super) attached along with the FEI VERIOS
36 460L. The HR-TEM imaging was carried out using a FEI TITAN Themis
37 60-300 high-based, Thermo Fisher Scientific operated at an acceleration
38 voltage of 300 kV. The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was
39 carried out using the Kratos AXIS Supra XPS machine. A monochromatic
40 Al K α (1486.7 eV) was used as an excitation source. The X-ray diffraction
41 (XRD) was performed using an X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku SmartLab
42 3 kW) using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm), operated at a current of
43 30 mA and a voltage of 40 kV. The BET surface area and pore size were
44 analyzed using NOVAtouch, Quantachrome instrument.

45 All the electrochemical measurements were carried out using a
46 potentiostat (Metrohm Autolab, PGSTAT 204, Netherlands) operated
47 by Nova 2.1.4 software. In the three-electrode test set up, the CV, GCD
48 and EIS measurements were carried out using Ag/AgCl in 1 M KCl as
49 reference electrode, Pt as counter electrode, and $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$ and
50 Ex- $Ti_3C_2T_x/CC$ as working electrodes. For Ex- $Ti_3C_2T_x/CC$ electrode, 1 mg
51 of active material was pasted on 1 cm² area of CC. For $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/$
52 CC electrode, total material mass was 32.2 mg and cross-sectional
53 area of 2 cm². The areal and gravimetric capacitances of the electrodes
54 were calculated following Equation S4 (Supporting Information).
55 The CV study of the blank CC in H_2SO_4 is shown in Figure S7a
56 (Supporting Information) and a comparison of cyclic voltammograms
57 of blank CC against $Ti_3C_2T_x/CC$ and $MoS_{3-x}@3DnCF/CC$ are shown in
58 Figure S7b (Supporting Information) at the scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. The
59 electrochemical analysis of the SS-ASC cell was measured following two-
electrode set up. The areal, volumetric and gravimetric capacitances
and corresponding energy density and power density were calculated
following Equations S5–S8 (Supporting Information).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or
from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors Contributions

K.G. carried out all synthesis, characterizations, and analysis. M.P. conceptualized and supervised the project. Both authors contributed to writing.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

Keywords

3D printing, asymmetric supercapacitors, MoS₂, MXene, solid state, Ti₃C₂, TMDs

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- [1] S. Chu, A. Majumdar, *Nature* **2012**, 488, 294.
- [2] C. Liu, F. Li, L. P. Ma, H. M. Cheng, *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, 22, 28.
- [3] J. R. Miller, P. Simon, *Sci. Mag.* **2008**, 321, 651.
- [4] B. E. Conway, *Electrochemical Supercapacitor*, Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers, New York **1999**.
- [5] M. R. Lukatskaya, O. Mashtalir, C. E. Ren, Y. Dall'Agnese, P. Rozier, P. L. Taberna, M. Naguib, P. Simon, M. W. Barsoum, Y. Gogotsi, *Science* **2013**, 341, 1502.
- [6] B. Anasori, M. R. Lukatskaya, Y. Gogotsi, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2017**, 2, 16098.
- [7] D. Xiong, X. Li, Z. Bai, S. Lu, *Small* **2018**, 14, 1703419.
- [8] X. Gao, X. Du, T. S. Mathis, M. Zhang, X. Wang, J. Shui, Y. Gogotsi, M. Xu, *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, 11, 6160.
- [9] X. Wang, S. Kajiyama, H. Iinuma, E. Hosono, S. Oro, I. Moriguchi, M. Okubo, A. Yamada, *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, 6, 6544.
- [10] Y. Wang, X. Wang, X. Li, X. Li, Y. Liu, Y. Bai, H. Xiao, G. Yuan, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2021**, 31, 2008185.
- [11] Q. Yun, L. Li, Z. Hu, Q. Lu, B. Chen, H. Zhang, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, 32, 1903826.
- [12] H. Wang, H. Feng, J. Li, *Small* **2014**, 10, 2165.
- [13] X. Wang, H. Li, H. Li, S. Lin, W. Ding, X. Zhu, Z. Sheng, H. Wang, X. Zhu, Y. Sun, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, 30, 0190302.

- [14] M. Naguib, M. Kurtoglu, V. Presser, J. Lu, J. Niu, M. Heon, L. Hultman, Y. Gogotsi, M. W. Barsoum, *Adv. Mater.* **2011**, 23, 4248.
- [15] Y. Zhong, X. Xia, F. Shi, J. Zhan, J. Tu, H. J. Fan, *Adv. Sci.* **2016**, 3, 1500286.
- [16] D. Wang, Y. Gao, Y. Liu, Y. Gogotsi, X. Meng, G. Chen, Y. Wei, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2017**, 5, 24720.
- [17] M. R. Lukatskaya, S. Kota, Z. Lin, M.-Q. Zhao, N. Shpigel, M. D. Levi, J. Halim, P.-L. Taberna, M. W. Barsoum, P. Simon, *Nat. Energy* **2017**, 2, 17105.
- [18] H. Yu, Y. Wang, Y. Jing, J. Ma, C. F. Du, Q. Yan, *Small* **2019**, 15, 1901503.
- [19] J. Yang, W. Bao, P. Jaumaux, S. Zhang, C. Wang, G. Wang, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, 6, 1802004.
- [20] Q. Yang, Z. Xu, B. Fang, T. Huang, S. Cai, H. Chen, Y. Liu, K. Gopalsamy, W. Gao, C. Gao, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2017**, 5, 22113.
- [21] J. Zhang, S. Seyedin, Z. Gu, W. Yang, X. Wang, J. M. Razal, *Nanoscale* **2017**, 9, 18604.
- [22] A. Byeon, M.-Q. Zhao, C. E. Ren, J. Halim, S. Kota, P. Urbankowski, B. Anasori, M. W. Barsoum, Y. Gogotsi, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, 9, 4296.
- [23] D. Er, J. Li, M. Naguib, Y. Gogotsi, V. B. Shenoy, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2014**, 6, 11173.
- [24] Y. Zhang, L. Zhang, T. a. Lv, P. K. Chu, K. Huo, *ChemSusChem* **2020**, 13, 1114.
- [25] J. Xu, Q. Wang, X. Wang, Q. Xiang, B. Liang, D. Chen, G. Shen, *ACS Nano* **2013**, 7, 5453.
- [26] M. Q. Zhao, X. Xie, C. E. Ren, T. Makaryan, B. Anasori, G. Wang, Y. Gogotsi, *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, 29, 1702410.
- [27] C. E. Ren, M. Q. Zhao, T. Makaryan, J. Halim, M. Boota, S. Kota, B. Anasori, M. W. Barsoum, Y. Gogotsi, *ChemElectroChem* **2016**, 3, 689.
- [28] J. Yan, Z. Fan, W. Sun, G. Ning, T. Wei, Q. Zhang, R. Zhang, L. Zhi, F. Wei, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2012**, 22, 2632.
- [29] M. Saraf, K. Natarajan, S. M. Mobin, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, 10, 16588.
- [30] C. Zhou, J. Wang, X. Yan, X. Yuan, D. Wang, Y. Zhu, X. Cheng, *Ceram. Int.* **2019**, 45, 21534.
- [31] L. Cao, S. Yang, W. Gao, Z. Liu, Y. Gong, L. Ma, G. Shi, S. Lei, Y. Zhang, S. Zhang, *Small* **2013**, 9, 2905.
- [32] E. Redondo, S. Ng, J. Muñoz, M. Pumera, *Nanoscale* **2020**, 12, 19673.
- [33] W. Gao, M. Pumera, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2021**, 31, 2007285.
- [34] K. Ghosh, M. Pumera, *Nanoscale* **2021**.
- [35] C. Y. Foo, H. N. Lim, M. A. Mahdi, M. H. Wahid, N. M. Huang, *Sci. Rep.* **2018**, 8, 7399.
- [36] C. W. Foster, M. P. Down, Y. Zhang, X. Ji, S. J. Rowley-Neale, G. C. Smith, P. J. Kelly, C. E. Banks, *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, 7, 42233.
- [37] R. Gusmão, M. P. Browne, Z. Sofer, M. Pumera, *Electrochem. Commun.* **2019**, 102, 83.
- [38] D. M. Wirth, M. J. Sheaff, J. V. Waldman, M. P. Symcox, H. D. Whitehead, J. D. Sharp, J. R. Doerfler, A. A. Lamar, G. LeBlanc, *Anal. Chem.* **2019**, 91, 5553.
- [39] F. Novotný, V. Urbanová, J. Plutnar, M. Pumera, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, 11, 35371.
- [40] K. Ghosh, S. Ng, C. Iffelsberger, M. Pumera, *Chem. - Eur. J.* **2020**, 26, 15746.
- [41] M. P. Browne, F. Novotný, Z. k. Sofer, M. Pumera, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, 10, 40294.
- [42] A. Yan, J. Velasco Jr, S. Kahn, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, F. Wang, M. F. Crommie, A. Zettl, *Nano Lett.* **2015**, 15, 6324.
- [43] Y. H. Lee, X. Q. Zhang, W. Zhang, M. T. Chang, C. T. Lin, K. D. Chang, Y. C. Yu, J. T. W. Wang, C. S. Chang, L. J. Li, *Adv. Mater.* **2012**, 24, 2320.
- [44] B. D. Falola, T. Wiltowski, I. I. Suni, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2016**, 163, D568.

- 1 [45] E. Ponomarev, M. Neumann-Spallart, G. Hodes, C. Lévy-Clément, *Thin Solid Films* **1996**, *280*, 86. 1
- 2 [46] A. Albu-Yaron, C. Lévy-Clément, A. Katty, S. Bastide, R. Tenne, *Thin Solid Films* **2000**, *361*, 223. 2
- 3 [47] X. Li, L. Yuan, R. Liu, H. He, J. Hao, Y. Lu, Y. Wang, G. Liang, 3
- 4 G. Yuan, Z. Guo, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2021**, *11*, 2003010. 4
- 5 [48] M. Naguib, O. Mashtalir, J. Carle, V. Presser, J. Lu, L. Hultman, 5
- 6 Y. Gogotsi, M. W. Barsoum, *ACS Nano* **2012**, *6*, 1322. 6
- 7 [49] X. Zhao, M. Liu, Y. Chen, B. Hou, N. Zhang, B. Chen, N. Yang, 7
- 8 K. Chen, J. Li, L. An, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2015**, *3*, 7870. 8
- 9 [50] M. Ghidui, M. R. Lukatskaya, M.-Q. Zhao, Y. Gogotsi, 9
- 10 M. W. Barsoum, *Nature* **2014**, *516*, 78. 10
- 11 [51] J. Halim, K. M. Cook, M. Naguib, P. Eklund, Y. Gogotsi, J. Rosen, 11
- 12 M. W. Barsoum, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2016**, *362*, 406. 12
- 13 [52] A. Pazniak, P. Bazhin, N. Shplis, E. Kolesnikov, I. Shchetinin, A. Komissarov, 13
- 14 J. Polcak, A. Stolín, D. Kuznetsov, *Mater. Des.* **2019**, *183*, 108143. 14
- 15 [53] M. Benchakar, L. Loupias, C. Garnero, T. Bilyk, C. Morais, C. Canaff, 15
- 16 N. Guignard, S. Morisset, H. Pazniak, S. Hurand, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 16
- 17 **2020**, *530*, 147209. 17
- 18 [54] I. Persson, L.-Å. Näslund, J. Halim, M. W. Barsoum, V. Darakchieva, 18
- 19 J. Palisaitis, J. Rosen, P. O. Å. Persson, *2D Mater.* **2017**, *5*, 015002. 19
- 20 [55] T. Schultz, N. C. Frey, K. Hantanasirisakul, S. Park, S. J. May, 20
- 21 V. B. Shenoy, Y. Gogotsi, N. Koch, *Chem. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 6590. 21
- 22 [56] J. Ma, W. Li, B. J. Morgan, J. Świątowska, R. Baddour-Hadjean, 22
- 23 M. Body, C. Legein, O. J. Borkiewicz, S. Leclerc, H. Groult, *Chem.* 23
- 24 *Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 3078. 24
- 25 [57] J. Liu, J. Essner, J. Li, *Chem. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 5022. 25
- 26 [58] C. J. Raj, M. Rajesh, R. Manikandan, J. Y. Sim, K. H. Yu, S. Y. Park, 26
- 27 J. H. Song, B. C. Kim, *Electrochim. Acta* **2017**, *247*, 949. 27
- 28 [59] S. Senthilkumar, R. K. Selvan, N. Ponpandian, J. Melo, *RSC Adv.* 28
- 29 **2012**, *2*, 8937. 29
- 30 [60] P. Taberna, P. Simon, J.-F. Fauvarque, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2003**, *150*, A292. 30
- 31 [61] M. P. Browne, V. Urbanova, J. Plutnar, F. Novotný, M. Pumera, *J.* 31
- 32 *Mater. Chem. A* **2020**, *8*, 1120. 32
- 33 [62] D. Belanger, G. Laperrière, B. Marsan, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **1993**, 33
- 34 *347*, 165. 34
- 35 [63] D. Belanger, G. Laperrière, F. Girard, D. Guay, G. Tourillon, *Chem.* 35
- 36 *Mater.* **1993**, *5*, 861. 36
- 37 [64] A. Ramadoss, S. J. Kim, *Carbon* **2013**, *63*, 434. 37
- 38 [65] V. Augustyn, J. Come, M. A. Lowe, J. W. Kim, P.-L. Taberna, 38
- 39 S. H. Tolbert, H. D. Abruña, P. Simon, B. Dunn, *Nat. Mater.* **2013**, 39
- 40 *12*, 518. 40
- 41 [66] R. Wang, S. Wang, X. Peng, Y. Zhang, D. Jin, P. K. Chu, L. Zhang, 41
- 42 *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *9*, 32745. 42
- 43 [67] Z. Le, F. Liu, P. Nie, X. Li, X. Liu, Z. Bian, G. Chen, H. B. Wu, Y. Lu, 43
- 44 *ACS Nano* **2017**, *11*, 2952. 44
- 45 [68] B. E. Conway, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **1991**, *138*, 1539. 45
- 46 [69] T. Brezesinski, J. Wang, S. H. Tolbert, B. Dunn, *Nat. Mater.* **2010**, 46
- 47 *9*, 146. 47
- 48 [70] Y. Jiang, J. Liu, *Energy Environ. Mater.* **2019**, *2*, 30. 48
- 49 [71] N. Wang, J. Liu, Y. Zhao, M. Hu, R. Qin, G. Shan, *ChemNanoMat* 49
- 50 **2019**, *5*, 658. 50
- 51 [72] N. Kurra, B. Ahmed, Y. Gogotsi, H. N. Alshareef, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 51
- 52 **2016**, *6*, 1601372. 52
- 53 [73] L. Ma, T. Zhao, F. Xu, T. You, X. Zhang, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2021**, 53
- 54 *405*, 126694. 54
- 55 [74] C. Zhang, M. P. Kremer, A. Seral-Ascaso, S. H. Park, N. McEvoy, 55
- 56 B. Anasori, Y. Gogotsi, V. Nicolosi, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2018**, 56
- 57 *28*, 1705506. 57
- 58 [75] Q. Jiang, N. Kurra, M. Alhabeb, Y. Gogotsi, H. N. Alshareef, *Adv.* 58
- 59 *Energy Mater.* **2018**, *8*, 1703043. 59
- 60 [76] W. Zhao, J. Peng, W. Wang, B. Jin, T. Chen, S. Liu, Q. Zhao, 60
- 61 W. Huang, *Small* **2019**, *15*, 1901351. 61
- 62 [77] J. Vyskočil, C. C. Mayorga-Martinez, K. Szókölová, A. Dash, 62
- 63 J. Gonzalez-Julian, Z. Sofer, M. Pumera, *ChemElectroChem* **2019**, 63
- 64 *6*, 3982. 64
- 65 [78] J. V. Vaghasiya, C. C. Mayorga-Martinez, J. Vyskočil, Z. Sofer, 65
- 66 M. Pumera, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 2003673. 66
- 67 [79] C. Iffelsberger, S. Ng, M. Pumera, *Appl. Mater. Today* **2020**, 67
- 68 *20*, 100654. 68
- 69 [80] Z. S. Wu, A. Winter, L. Chen, Y. Sun, A. Turchanin, X. Feng, 69
- 70 K. Müllen, *Adv. Mater.* **2012**, *24*, 5130. 70